

SIVIM Floodplain Forests – Database of riverine forests and scrubs from the Iberian Peninsula

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Abstract

“SIVIM Floodplain Forests” (GIVD ID: EU-00-024) is a thematic database focused on vegetation plots of riverine forests and scrubs from the Iberian Peninsula and the Pyrenees (Spain, Portugal and southern France). It was registered in the GIVD in February 2016. The data are available both from EVA and sPlot in semi-restricted regime. The database includes both digitized relevés from the literature and unpublished data. Many digitized relevés were derived from SIVIM (GIVD ID EU-00-004) and BIOVEG (GIVD ID EU-00-011), with which SIVIM Floodplain Forests thus partly overlaps. Currently it contains 4,736 vegetation plots of floodplain forests, alder carrs, willow scrubs, and tamarisk and oleander thickets, 99% of them classified at association level. Plot size is available for 94.6% of the relevés. Plant taxonomy is standardized to Flora Iberica. The database has been used for studies on vegetation classification at Iberian and European level, as well as studies on plant invasion, fine-grain plant diversity and macroecological analyses, most of them via EVA.

Abbreviations: BIOVEG = Vegetation-Plot Database of the University of the Basque Country; EVA = European Vegetation Archive; GIVD = Global Index of Vegetation-Plot Databases; SIVIM = Iberian and Macaronesian Vegetation Information System.

Keywords

Alnetea glutinosae, *Alno glutinosae-Populetea albae*, floodplain forest, Iberian Peninsula, *Nerio-Tamaricetea*, Portugal, Pyrenees, relevé, *Salicetea purpureae*, Spain, vegetation-plot database, willow scrub

GIVD Fact Sheet

GIVD Database ID: EU-00-024		Last update: 2020-12-04	
Iberian and Macaronesian Vegetation Information System (SIVIM) – Floodplain Forests		Web address:	
Database manager(s): Idoia Biurrun (idoia.biurrun@ehu.es); Xavier Font (xfont@ub.edu)			
Owner: Idoia Biurrun			
Scope: Phytosociological relevés of floodplain forests, alder carrs, willow scrubs and tamarisk and oleander thickets in the Iberian Peninsula			
Abstract:			
Availability: according to a specific agreement		Online upload: no	Online search: no
Database format(s): TURBOVEG, MS Access, Excel, other, XML from B-VegAna		Export format(s): TURBOVEG, MS Access, Excel, XML from B-VegAna	
Plot type(s): normal plots		Plot-size range: 4 to 800	
Non-overlapping plots: 4736	Estimate of existing plots: 6000	Completeness: 79%	Status: ongoing capture
Total no. of plot observations: 4736	Number of sources (biblioreferences, data collectors): 275	Valid taxa: 2407	
Countries (%): ES: 84; PT: 15; FR: 1			
Formations: Forest: 75% = Terrestrial: 75% // Non Forest: 25% = Terrestrial: 25% (Non arctic-alpin: 25% [Natural: 25%])			
Guilds: all vascular plants: 100%			
Environmental data (%): altitude: 97			
Performance measure(s): presence/absence only: <1%; cover: >99%			
Geographic localisation: GPS coordinates (precision 25 m or less): 10%; point coordinates less precise than GPS, up to 1 km: 76%; small grid (not coarser than 10 km): 14%; political units or only on a coarser scale (above 10 km): 0.2%			
Sampling periods: before 1920: 0%; 1920-1929: 0%; 1930-1939: <0.1%; 1940-1949: 0.4%; 1950-1959: 1.6%; 1960-1969: 2.1%; 1970-1979: 3.7%; 1980-1989: 22.3%; 1990-1999: 34.2%; 2000-2009: 26.0%; 2010-2019: 9.4%; unknown: 0.2%			
<i>Information as of 2020-12-04 further details and future updates available from http://www.givd.info/ID/EU-00-024</i>			

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